
Avian Refuge in Urban Green Space: Diversity and Abundance of Psittacidae in GSG College Campus, Umarched, Maharashtra, India

Sandeep Chede¹, Dinesh Dabhadkar¹, Madhav Kalyankar¹, Nitin Raut²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Gopikabai Sitaram Gawande Mahavidyalaya, Umarched, Dist- Yavatmal, Maharashtra, India- 445 206

²Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Arvindbabu Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya, Bharsingi, Dist- Nagpur, Maharashtra, India- 441 305

Corresponding Author –Sandeep Chede

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Abstract:

The present study deals with diversity and abundance of parrot species within the GSG college campus, Umarched, Maharashtra, India. Over a three-month period (November 2024 to January 2025). The campus, characterized by a diverse flora including coconut, palm, neem, mango, eucalyptus, teak, and peepal trees, provides a rich habitat for avian species. Four prominent parrot species were observed: Alexandrine Parakeet (*Psittacula eupatria*), Plum-headed Parakeet (*Psittacula cyanocephala*), Rose-ringed Parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*), and Vernal Hanging Parrot (*Loriculus vernalis*). The Alexandrine Parakeet was identified as the dominant species. Observations included species identification, frequency of visits, and general behavior. This study highlights the importance of urban green spaces in supporting avian biodiversity and provides baseline data for future ecological monitoring.

Keywords: Abundance, Diversity, Parrot, Umarched, Species

Introduction:

Urban green spaces are increasingly recognized as vital refuges for wildlife, playing a critical role in biodiversity conservation amidst rapid urbanization (Hartig *et al.*, 2014). Parrots, as efficient seed dispersers, contribute significantly to forest regeneration and serve as valuable indicators of ecosystem health (Galetti, 1997). The present study focused on the GSG College campus, located in Umarched, Maharashtra, a region bordering Vidarbha and Marathwada. The campus is characterized by a rich and diverse flora, including mature trees such as coconut, palm, neem, mango, eucalyptus, teak, and peepal, creating a unique habitat for avian species. The primary objective of this research was to document the diversity and abundance of parrot species within the

campus. Observations conducted from November 2024 to January 2025 revealed the presence of four prominent parrot species like Alexandrine parakeet (*Psittacula eupatria*), a large, intelligent species native to the Indian subcontinent, known for its rose-colored nape and black neck ring in males; the Plum-headed parakeet (*Psittacula cyanocephala*), found in northern and central India, distinguished by the male's plum-colored head; the widely distributed Rose-ringed parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*), recognized by the male's distinct black ring and rose-colored collar; and the small, vibrant Vernal Hanging Parrot (*Loriculus vernalis*), found across the Indian subcontinent, (Royle *et al.*, 2004) with its bright green plumage and red rump. This study is small efforts to provide baseline data on the parrot diversity within this urban

green space and contribute to understanding the ecological role of such habitats.

Materials and Methods:

Study Area:

The study was conducted within the GSG College campus, located in Umarched (19.53°N, 77.70°E), Yavatmal district, Maharashtra, India. Umarched is situated at the border of the Vidarbha and Marathwada regions. The campus encompasses approximately (35 Acres) 14 hectares, characterized by a well-established and diverse green space within a semi-urban environment. The college campus is notable for its mature and varied vegetation, creating a rich habitat for avian fauna. Dominant tree species include:

SN	Botanical name	Common name
1	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Coconut
2	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i>	Palm
3	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem
4	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mango
5	<i>Eucalyptus spp.</i>	Eucalyptus
6	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Teak
7	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Peepal

Table: 1 Dominant tree species within campus

These trees provide a variety of food sources, including fruits, seeds, and nectar, as well as suitable nesting and roosting sites. The campus grounds include maintained lawns, buildings, and pathways, which are interspersed with the mature trees, creating a mosaic of habitats (Dhore and Joshi, 1988).

Fig 1: Map of GSG college campus showing the green spaces

The diverse flora combined with the college campus's location near the transition zone between Vidarbha and Marathwada regions creates a unique ecological setting for observing avian diversity.

Study Period:

The observational study was conducted over a three-month period, from November 1st, 2024, to January 31st, 2025. This period was selected to coincide with the post-monsoon and early winter seasons in the region. This time frame was chosen for several reasons:

Fruiting Season:

Many of the dominant tree species on the campus, such as mango and neem, produce fruits during this period, providing a rich food source for parrots.

Post-Monsoon Conditions:

The post-monsoon period typically experiences relatively stable weather conditions, facilitating consistent observations.

Avian Activity:

This period is known to be a time of increased avian activity in the region, including migratory movements and local foraging behaviors. Therefore, the chosen study period was deemed optimal for observing the diversity and abundance of parrot species utilizing the resources within the GSG College campus (Wadatkar *et al.*, 2024; Wagh and Prathmesh, 2020).

Data Collection:

Observations were conducted using direct visual observation methods. Point counts were employed to systematically record the presence and behavior of parrot species within the campus.

Observation Frequency and Duration:

Observations were carried out three times per week (Mondays, Wednesdays, and Fridays) during the study period. Each observation session lasted for two hours, conducted during the morning hours (07:00 to 09:00) and afternoon hours (15:00 to 17:00) to capture peak avian activity.

Observation points were chosen to cover the variety of habitat available within the campus (Wagh and Prathmesh, 2020).

Species Identification:

Species identification was primarily based on visual characteristics, including plumage color, size, and distinctive markings. Field guides specific to Indian birds, such as "Birds of the Indian Subcontinent" by Grimmett *et al.*, (2014) were used to confirm species identification. In cases of uncertainty, photographs were taken for later verification (Wadatkar *et al.*, 2024; Symes and Perrin, 2003).

Alexandrine parakeet

Plum-headed parakeet

Rose ringed parakeet

Vernal hanging parrot

Fig 2: Diversity of parrot species within campus

Data Analysis:

Frequency counts and relative abundance: The number of observations for each parrot species was recorded for each observation session. Total frequency counts

were calculated for each species over the entire study period. Relative abundance was determined by calculating the percentage of observations for each species relative to the

total number of parrot observations and data was compiled into tables and graphs.

Dominance Determination: Dominance was determined based on the relative abundance of each species. The species with the highest relative abundance was considered the dominant species. The species with the highest number of overall

observations was defined as the dominant species.

Results and Discussion:

A total of four parrot species were identified within the GSG College campus during the study period. These species along with their scientific and common names are listed in Table- 2.

S.N.	Scientific name	Common Name
1.	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	Alexandrine Parakeet
2.	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	Plum-headed Parakeet
3.	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Rose ringed Parakeet
4.	<i>Loriculus vernalis</i>	Vernal Hanging Parrot

Table 2: Parrot species diversity observed in GSG College campus

The frequency of visits for each parrot species was recorded throughout the study period. The total number of

observations and the calculated relative abundance are presented in Table - 3.

S.N.	Species (Scientific Name)	Total Observations	Relative Abundance (%)
1	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	92	100 %
2	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	79	85.86 %
3	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	77	83.69 %
4	<i>Loriculus vernalis</i>	56	60.86 %

Table 3: Frequency of observations and relative abundance of Parrot species

Graph 1: Showing relative abundance of parrot species

The Alexandrine Parakeet (*Psittacula eupatria*) was the dominant species, exhibiting the highest frequency of

visits and relative abundance within the campus.

Behavioral Observations:

Alexandrine Parakeet (*Psittacula eupatria*): Observed feeding on fruits of *Mangifera indica* (mango) and seeds of *Azadirachta indica* (neem). Roosted in tall *Eucalyptus spp.* trees, forming large flocks in the evenings. Social interactions included vocalizations, territorial disputes near food sources, and mutual preening.

Plum-headed Parakeet (*Psittacula cyanocephala*): Observed foraging for seeds and buds in *Ficus religiosa* (peepal) trees. Smaller flocks were observed, often moving through the campus in search of food. Social interactions were less frequent compared to the Alexandrine Parakeet.

Rose-ringed Parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*): Observed feeding on a variety of fruits and seeds, demonstrating adaptability in food sources. Roosted in *Cocos nucifera* (coconut) and *Borassus flabellifer* (palm) trees. Observed to be very vocal and form small groups.

Vernal Hanging Parrot (*Loriculus vernalis*): Observed feeding on nectar from flowers and small fruits. Often seen hanging upside down while feeding. Observed in the canopy of *Tectona grandis* (teak) trees. Observed in small groups.

Habitat use: *Mangifera indica* (mango) and *Azadirachta indica* (neem) trees were frequently utilized by Alexandrine Parakeets for feeding. *Ficus religiosa* (peepal) trees were frequented by Plum-headed Parakeets. *Cocos nucifera* (coconut) and *Borassus flabellifer* (palm) trees were used by Rose-ringed Parakeets for roosting. *Tectona grandis* (teak) trees were frequently used by Vernal Hanging Parrots. Tall *Eucalyptus spp.* trees provided preferred roosting sites for Alexandrine Parakeets.

This study revealed a notable diversity of parrot species within the GSG College campus, highlighting the importance of urban green spaces for avian conservation. The presence of four distinct parrot species, including the dominant

Alexandrine Parakeet, underscores the campus's role as a valuable habitat in an urban environment. The observed parrot diversity aligns with studies documenting the adaptability of *Psittacula* parakeets to human-modified landscapes (e.g., Shwartz *et al.*, 2014). The presence of *Alexandrine*, *Rose-ringed*, and *Plum-headed Parakeets* is consistent with their reported distributions across the Indian subcontinent (Grimmett *et al.*, 2016). The presence of the *Vernal hanging parrot* highlights the diversity of habitats available within the campus.

Role of GSG College Campus as Habitat:

The GSG College campus serves as a crucial habitat for parrot species in the Umarkhed region. The diverse vegetation and mature trees provide essential resources for feeding, roosting, and breeding. The campus acts as a green oasis, offering refuge from the surrounding urban and agricultural landscapes. The dominance of the *Alexandrine Parakeet* can be attributed to several factors: **Size and Adaptability:** *Alexandrine Parakeets* are larger and more adaptable than other observed species, enabling them to exploit a wider range of food sources and habitats. **Social Behavior:** Their strong social behavior and flocking tendencies may provide them with a competitive advantage. **Vocalizations:** Their vocalizations may help them maintain territory and communicate within their flocks. **Food Resources:** The size of the *Alexandrine Parakeet* allows it to consume larger fruits and seeds. **Ecological significance:** The observed parrot species play vital ecological roles. **Seed Dispersal:** Parrots are important seed dispersers, contributing to the regeneration of plant communities. **Ecosystem Indicators:** Their presence and abundance can indicate the health and biodiversity of the ecosystem. **Food Chain:** Parrots serve as prey for various predators contributing to the food web.

Conclusion:

The present work deals with documentation of presence of four distinct parrot species within the GSG College campus, Umarkhed, Maharashtra, highlighting the ecological significance of urban green spaces. The Alexandrine Parakeet emerged as the dominant species, reflecting its adaptability and resource utilization. The diverse flora of the campus including mature trees such as mango, neem and eucalyptus provides essential resources for feeding, roosting and social interactions of these avian species. This research underscores the vital role of urban green spaces in supporting avian biodiversity particularly in rapidly developing regions. The findings of this study highlight the importance of preserving and enhancing urban green spaces for biodiversity conservation. College campuses, parks and gardens can serve as valuable habitats for avian species. Maintaining and increasing the diversity of native tree species can further enhance the ecological value of these urban green spaces.

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